

The Hattic language is close to the Yeniseian languages not to the Northwest Caucasian languages. The Hattians were a branch of the ancient ‘Yeniseians’

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Abstract

Within the Sino-Caucasian macrofamily, Hattic is close to the Yeniseian languages than to Northwest Caucasian. For instance, in Hattic transitive verbs, the agent marker precedes the patient marker; conversely, in Adyghe, the patient marker comes before the agent marker. The system of Hattic subject/agent markers doesn't demonstrate much similarity with the system of absolutive/ergative markers of Adyghe but bears a striking resemblance to the Ket series of *ba-/bo-* markers. In Hattic, negation is expressed by the prefix *taš/šaš/teš/šeš*, which occupies the leftmost position correlates with the Ket prepositional prohibitive marker *at/atn*. The Hattic optative marker, the prefix *ta-/te-*, which occupies a near-leftmost position correlates with the Ket prepositional optative marker *qan*. Beyond grammatical similarities, there are also notable lexical resemblances. Moreover, and what is especially important, Hattic theonyms have clear Yeniseian etymologies.

Keywords: Hattic language; Northwest Caucasian languages; Yeniseian languages; Ainu-Minoan macrofamily; Sino-Caucasian macrofamily; comparative linguistics

1. Introduction to the problem

Within the Sino-Caucasian (Ainu-Minoan) macrofamily, Hattic was traditionally considered to be closely related to the Northwest Caucasian (Abkhaz-Adyghe) languages. I.M. Dunaevskaya, Vyach. Vs. Ivanov, and V.G. Ardzinba pointed to a number of structural and lexical similarities between Hattic and the Northwest Caucasian languages (Dunaevskaya 1960.; Ivanov 1985, Ardzinba 1979).

However, recently there has been a growing understanding that Hattic does not demonstrate any particular closeness to the Abkhaz-Adyghe languages, but rather constitutes a separate branch within the Sino-Caucasian macrofamily.

A. Kassian and A. Akulov independently of each other and using different linguistic methods, came to the same conclusion that Hattic does not demonstrate any particular closeness to the Northwest Caucasian languages.

Kassian examines mainly the lexical layers and points out that within the Sino-Caucasian macrofamily, Hattic does not demonstrate any particular closeness to the Northwest Caucasian languages, but is even closer to the Yeniseian languages (Kassian 2009 – 2010)

Akulov, compares Hattic and Kabardian languages with the use of such a structural-typological parameter as the index of verbal grammar correlation and shows that Hattic and Kabardian

demonstrate the same distance as Kabardinian and Qiang, English and Persian, that is, they are, in general, quite distant relatives (Akulov 2018).

Also, it is noteworthy that among some Adyghe and Abkhaz, the notion that the Hattic language practically a branch of the Northwest Caucasian, and that the Hattic language could be an ancestor of the modern Adyghe or Abkhaz languages. These notions are highly mythologized, but have no basis in reality. They are based, firstly, on a completely incorrect, biased understanding of linguists' works (for example, Ardzinba, when compared Hattic with the Abkhaz-Adyghe languages, spoke only of its relationship to Abkhaz-Adyghe, but never wrote that Hattic is the direct ancestor of modern Northwest Caucasian), and, secondly, on a strong desire to embellish their ancient history and claim 'great' ancestors.

In this paper I want to show that the Hattic language doesn't demonstrate many resemblances with Northwest Caucasian, but instead demonstrate notorious similarities with the Yeniseian languages.

2. Comparing Hattic, Adyghe and Ket languages

To show that Hattic differs significantly from the Abkhaz-Adyghe languages, but is quite close to the Yeniseian languages in structural terms, I will compare Hattic with the Adyghe language and with Ket language.

It would be more correct to compare Hattic grammar with Proto-Northwest Caucasian and Proto-Yeniseian grammars. However, at present I am not aware of any satisfactory reconstructions of Proto-Northwest Caucasian and Proto-Yeniseian grammars. People involved in reconstructions of proto-languages usually focus on reconstructing vocabulary and phonetics and do not engage in reconstructing the structural-grammatical level at all.

That's why in the current comparison I will compare Hattic with Adyghe and Ket.

2.1. Comparing structures of Hattic, Adyghe and Ket verbs

Since the basic element of any language is the verb, in this case the main attention is paid to the comparison of verb word-forms.

At first glance the structures of the Hattic and Adyghe verbs are very similar, for example, both can have up to 9 prefixes, but positional distributions and material implementations of specific grammatical markers in the Hattic and Adyghe verbs differ significantly.

The linear model of the Adyghe verb word-form is shown in the Table 1.

-9	-8	-7	-6	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4	5
Abs.	Dir.	Temp.	Ob.	Ind. Ob.	Ag.	Opt.	Neg.	Caus.	R.	Inc.	Prop.	Pl.	Dyn. Sfx.	Neg. Sfx.
						Dyn. Prfx.								

Table. 1. The linear model of Adyghe verb word-form, the table has been created after Arkadiev et al 2009: 42); Abs. – absolutive personal prefix (i.e.: personal marker of subject of intransitive verbs), Dir. – directive prefix, Temp. – temporal prefix, Ob. – object, Ind. Ob. – indirect object, Ag. – agent, Opt. – optative, Neg. – negation, Dyn. Prfx. – dynamic prefix, Caus. – causative, R. – root, Inc. – incorporated elements, Prop. – propositional operators, Dyn. Sfx. – dynamic suffix, Neg. Sfx. – negative suffix

The linear model of the Hattic verb word-form is shown in the Table 2.

-9	-8	-7	-6	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2
Neg.	Opt.	Sb.	Ref.	Ob.	Loc.1	Loc.2	Loc.3	?	R.	T.A.M.	Part.

Table. 2. The linear model of Hattic verb word-form, the table has been created after (Kassian 2010: 178); Neg. – negation, Opt. – optative, Sb. – subject, Ref. – reflexive, Ob. – object, Loc. – marker of place, R. – root, T. A.M. – tense, aspect, mood, Part. – particles

In Ket verb word-form there can be up to 8 prefixes (Vajda 2004: 45).

2.1.1. Positions distributions of agent, subject and patient markers inside a transitive verb

In Hattic, as in Adyghe, transitive verbs use special markers to express the person and number of the agent and patient. However, the positions of the agent and patient in Hattic and Adyghe differ significantly, and the material exponents also differ significantly.

In the Hattic language, in a transitive verb, the prefix denoting agent comes first, and only then the prefix denoting the object/patient, in Adyghe it's exactly the opposite: the prefix expressing the object is to the left of the prefix expressing the agent.

Adyghe

-9	-8	-7	-6	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4	5
Abs.	Dir.	Temp.	Ob.	Ind. Ob.	Ag.	Opt.	Neg.	Caus.	R.	Inc.	Prop.	Pl.	Dyn. Sfx.	Neg. Sfx.
						Dyn.Prfx.								

agent direct object (patient)

-9	-8	-7	-6	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2
Neg.	Opt.	Sb.	Ref.	Ob.	Loc.1	Loc.2	Loc.3	?	R.	T.A.M.	Part.

Hattic

Fig. 1. Comparing positional realizations of agent and direct object (patient) in Hattic and in Adyghe

In Ket language transitive verbs also bear markers of agent and patient, and their positional distribution is similar to that of Hattic, i.e.: in a transitive verb word-form agent always occupies leftmost position. For example:

di-in-ku-tet

1sg.ag.-PAST-2sg.pt.-hit

"I hit you (singular)" (Vajda 2004: 49)

da-o-in-tet

3sg.ag.f.-3sg.pt.m.-PAST-hit

“she hit him” (Vajda2004: 49)

It is also noteworthy that in Hattic the agent of a transitive verb and the subject of an intransitive verb are expressed in the same position, while in Adyghe the markers expressing the subject of an intransitive verb (absolute markers) occupy the leftmost position, a position different from the position that serves to express the agent (see Fig. 1).

2.1.2. The systems of agent/subject markers

Hattic uses the same series of personal markers to express both the agent of a transitive verb and the subject of an intransitive verb, while Adyghe has two different sets of markers: agent and subject markers.

And also, material implementations of Hattic subject/agent markers and Adyghe absolutive and ergative markers demonstrate less similarity than Hattic subject/agent markers and Ket personal markers of *ba-/bo-* series (see Table 3, Fig.2).

	Adyghe		Hattic	Ket
	Abs.	Erg.		
1sg	sə-	s-	fa-	ba- / bo-
2pl	tə-	t-	ai-/e-/i-	dəŋ-
2sg	wə-	w- / p-	u- / un-	ku-
2pl	ʃwə-	ʃw-	?	kəŋ-
3sg	-----	ə- / jə-	∅- (or a- ?)	3m.: a- / o- / bu- 3f: i- / o- / bu- 3 in.: ∅- / i- / u- / bu-
3pl	-----	a-	∅- (or a- ?)	3. an.: pl. aŋ- / oŋ- / bu- 3 in.: ∅- / i- / u- / bu-

Table 3. Comparing of Adyghe absolutive (Abs.) and ergative (Erg.) markers with Hattic subject markers, m. – masculine, f. – feminine, in. – inanimate, an. – animate (Adyghe part created after Arkadiev et al 2009: 45, Hattic after Kassian 2010: 179, and Ket after Vajda 2004: 48)

(In the Ket verb there are different series of personal markers that can express different meanings, the markers of *ba-/bo-* series can function as active intransitive subject and inactive intransitive subject Vajda 2004: 48.)

Thus, the system of Hattic markers of subject/agent doesn't demonstrate much similarity with the system of absolutive/ergative markers of Adyghe, but demonstrates quite notorious similarity with the Ket series of *ba-/bo-* markers (see Fig. 2).

	Adyghe		Hattic	Ket
	Abs.	Erg.		
1sg	sə-	s-	fa-	ba- / bo-
2pl	tə-	t-	ai-/e-/i-	dəŋ-
2sg	wə-	w- / p-	u- / un-	ku-
2pl	š _w ə-	š _w -	?	kəŋ-
3sg	-----	ə- / jə-	∅- (or a- ?)	3m.: a- / o- / bu- 3f: i- / o- / bu- 3 in.: ∅- / i- / u- / bu-
3pl	-----	a-	∅- (or a- ?)	3. an.: pl. aŋ- / oŋ- / bu- 3 in.: ∅- / i- / u- / bu-

Fig. 2. A scheme showing that there are more similarities between systems of personal markers of Hattic and Ket (red lines), than between systems of personal markers of Hattic and Adyghe (blue lines)

2.1.3. Negation

There is also a significant difference in the ways of expressing negation (see Fig. 3).

In Hattic, negation is expressed by the prefix *taš/šaš/teš/šeš*, which occupies the leftmost position (Kassian 2010: 178), forms *šaš/teš/šeš* evidently are just variants of the form *taš*.

In Adyghe, negation is expressed by the prefix *mə-*, which expresses negation in syntactically subordinate non-finite forms and occupies position -2 (Arkadiev et al 2009: 42, 45), and by the suffix *-ep*, which expresses negation in finite (non-subordinate) forms and occupies position 5 (Arkadiev et al 2009: 42, 47).

Adyghe														
-9	-8	-7	-6	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4	5
Abs.	Dir.	Temp.	Ob.	Ind. Ob.	Ag.	Opt.	Neg.	Caus.	R.	Inc.	Prop.	Pl.	Dyn. Sfx.	Neg. Sfx.
							<i>mə-</i>							<i>-ep</i>

Hattic											
-9	-8	-7	-6	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2
Neg.	Opt.	Sb.	Ref.	Ob.	Loc.1	Loc.2	Loc.3	?	R.	T.A.M.	Part.
<i>taš-</i>											

Fig. 3. Scheme showing dissimilarity in positional distributions of markers of negations in Adyghe and Hattic verbs

On the other hand in Ket verb negation is expressed by prepositional particle *bən*, and also in Ket there is prepositional prohibitive marker *at/atn* (Werner 1997: 184).

Any prepositional particle actually occupies the leftmost position in the verb word-form and can be described as prefix.

Thus, Hattic *taš/saš* correlates well with Ket *at/atn*, and has no counterparts in Adyghe.

2.1.4. Optative

There is also a significant difference in the ways the optative is expressed. In Hattic optative is expressed with the prefix *ta-/te-*, which occupies the eighth position to the left of the root (Kassian 2010: 1786 179). In Adyghe optative is expressed with the prefix *(w)ere*, which occupies the third position to the left of the root (Arkadiev et al 2009: 45, see also Fig.4).

Adyghe

-9	-8	-7	-6	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4	5
Abs.	Dir.	Temp.	Ob.	Ind. Ob.	Ag.	Opt.	Neg.	Caus.	R.	Inc.	Prop.	Pl.	Dyn. Sfx.	Neg. Sfx.
						Dyn.Prfx.								

(w)ere

-9	-8	-7	-6	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2
Neg.	Opt.	Sb.	Ref.	Ob.	Loc.1	Loc.2	Loc.3	?	R.	T.A.M.	Part.
	<i>ta/te</i>										

Hattic

Fig. 4. Scheme showing the dissimilarity in positional distributions and materials implementations of Hattic and Adyghe optative markers

There is a significant difference in the material exponents and a significant difference in the positional realizations. This difference in position is insignificant if we say that the languages belong to the same family/macrolanguage and are distantly related, but it is significant if we assume that the languages being compared are supposed to be closely related (belong to the same group).

On the other hand in Ket optative is expressed by the particle *qan* that is placed immediately before a finite indicative verb form (George 2007: 298).

As it has been noted above, a prepositional particle can be described as a prefix occupying the leftmost position.

Hattic and Ket optative markers demonstrate notorious similarity both in positions and in material implementations: the distance between *ta/te* and *qan* evidently is much less than that between *ta/te* and *(w)ere*.

2.1.5. Ways of expressing of tenses and aspects

In Hattic, aspectual-temporal meanings are expressed by suffixes occupying the first position to the right of the root (see Table 2).

At present, there is no complete clarity regarding the Hattic tense-aspect system yet, but it is supposed that tense-aspect meanings were expressed in the Hattic language using suffixes (Kassian 2010: 178, 180).

In Adyghe, aspectual-temporal meanings are expressed mostly by suffixes, and at first glance this system perfectly corresponds to the Hattic system. However, in Adyghe, unlike Hattic, tense can also be expressed by prefixes. For example, it is said that dynamic prefix can be used to indicate the present tense of dynamic verbs in Adyghe (Arkadiev et al 2009: 56). Also tenses and aspects can be expressed by auxiliary stems incorporated to the main root (Arkadiev et al 2009: 57).

On the other hand in Ket tenses and aspects are expressed by a standard set of prefixes.

From the point of view of standardness, the Hattic system is similar to the Ket system, but the Ket language expresses tense using prefixes, while Hattic uses suffixes.

In terms of positional distributions, the Hattic system is much alike to the Adyghe system, but the Adyghe system differs from the Hattic system in its greater irregularity and diversity.

I have to say that the Hattic system of expressing aspectual and temporal meanings generally does not exhibit significant similarities neither with Adyghe, nor with Ket. In this case, it can be said that Hattic is equidistant from both Adyghe and Ket.

In this brief overview, I have examined only the most striking examples demonstrating the significant differences in the grammatical systems of the Hattic and Adyghe languages. A full comparative analysis of the grammatical systems of verbs of the two languages, and then the grammatical systems of nouns, would reveal even more structural and material differences.

However, the differences already identified are sufficient to understand that all assertions about the special closeness of Hattic and Abkhaz-Adyghe are completely incorrect and have no real basis.

It is categorically incorrect to claim that Hattic is the ancestor of the Adyghe languages or an Adyghe 'dialect'. Hattic does not show any particular similarities with the Abkhaz-Adyghe languages. Hattic and the Abkhaz-Adyghe languages are related, but they are related as two distinct branches/groups within the Sino-Caucasian family.

2.2. Comparing of lexis

As it has been noted above, Kassian, basing on a comparison of lexis and individual morphemes, came to the conclusion that within the Sino-Caucasian macrofamily Hattic is closer to the Yeniseian languages rather than to the North Caucasian languages.

Kassian includes Hattic into the Yeniseian – Burushaski branch, but he points out that formal lexicostatistic evidence are yet insufficient for unambiguous conclusion (see Kassian 2009 – 2010: 430).

I have to note that comparison of lexis made by Kassian is actually rather haphazard, and from the linguistic material presented in the work, sometimes it is quite difficult to discern that Hattic is specifically close to the Proto-Yeniseian language. In several cases, Kassian compares the Hattic form only to Proto-Yeniseian and simply postulates that corresponding forms are absent in the North-Caucasian languages, and it is supposed that readers would take his word for it.

Of course, sometimes it can be quite a complicated task to decide whether a certain Hattic form is closer to Proto-Yeniseian or to Proto-North-Caucasian, but here can help calculation degree of similarity between two forms.

My task is much easier than that of Kassian since I want just to show that Hattic is closer to Proto-Yeniseian than to Proto-Northwest Caucasian.

To show how close Hattic is to the Proto-Yeniseian language and not close to the Proto-Northwest language at the lexical level, I will now take several Hattic words and compare them with Proto-Yeniseian and Proto-Northwest Caucasian forms.

“big”

Hattic **te / *ti* “sublime”, “great”, “big” (Soysal 2004: 313) correlates with Proto-Yeniseian **tij-* “to grow”¹, the corresponding Proto-Norwest Caucasian form is **dA* “big”.

Kassian also compares Hattic **te / *ti* with Proto-Yeniseian **tij-* and Proto-Norwest Caucasian form is **dA* “big” (see Kassian 2009 – 2010: 363)

The Hattic form is closer to Proto-Yeniseian than to Proto-Abkhaz-Adyghe.

“to come”

Hattic *aš* (Soysal 2004: 275) correlates well with Proto-Yeniseian **ʔēč-* “to let come”.

The corresponding Proto-Northwest Caucasian form is **šə* “move”, “pass”, “come”, “reach”.

Kassian also compares Hattic *aš* with Proto-Yeniseian **ʔēč-* (Kassian 2009 – 2010: 341 – 342) and also gives Proto-Northwest Caucasian form **ča* (~ **č-*) “to go”, “to walk” (Kassian 2009 – 2010: 342).

The Hattic form is closer to Proto-Yeniseian than to Proto-Northwest Caucasian.

“Moon”

Hattic *kap* “Moon” correlates with Proto-Yeniseian **χ[e]p* “Moon” (Kassian 2009 – 2010: 345), Kassian reconstructs the form **q[e]p* for the Proto-Yeniseian “Moon” (Kassian 2009 – 2010: 345).

Kassian doesn’t show Proto-North-Caucasian correspondences for this example.

The Proto-Northwest Caucasian form for “Moon” is **mVza*.

The Hattic form is very close to the Proto-Yeniseian and is completely different from the Proto-Abkhaz-Adyghe.

“mountain”

Hattic *ziš* “mountain” (Soysal 2004: 329) correlates well with Proto-Yeniseian **čʔs* “stone”. In

¹ As far as databases with reconstructions of Proto-Yeniseian and Proto-Northwest Caucasian are unavailable now, all Proto-Yeniseian and Proto-Northwest Caucasian forms shown in this article have been received with the use of AI systems.

Proto-Northwest Caucasian, at least two forms with the meaning "stone" are reconstructed: **χaq:wə* and **məzʷa*.

For the word "rock" in Proto-Northwest Caucasian, the following form is reconstructed **b(ə)žʷa*.

Also, at least three forms with the meaning "mountain" are reconstructed for Proto-Northwest Caucasian:

- 1) **łV* "mountain", "high",
- 2) **xʷA* "mountain", "hill",
- 3) **qIʷV* "mountain", "cave".

Kassian also compares Hattic *ziš* with Proto-Yeniseian **čʰʔs*, and notes that the corresponding Proto-North Caucasian form is **čǎčwV* is quite distant from Hattic and Yeniseian both phonetically and semantically (Kassian 2009 – 2010: 368).

The Hattic word for "mountain" is very similar to the Proto-Yeniseian word for "stone" and is completely different from the Proto-Abkhaz-Adyghe forms with similar meanings.

"to protect"

Hattic *kip* "to protect" (Soysal 2004: 288) correlates with Proto-Yeniseian **qepVn*- "close the door".

The corresponding Proto-Northwest Caucasian form is **qʷə* "to button up".

Kassian also compares Hattic *kip* with Proto-Yeniseian **qepVn* and also with Proto-North Caucasian form **q[ä]pV* "to cover" (Kassian 2009 – 2010: 346).

The Hattic form is clearly closer to Proto-Yeniseian than to Proto-Northwest Caucasian.

"sea"

Hattic *han* "sea" (Soysal 2004: 277) correlates well with Proto-Yeniseian **ʔän* "wave". The Proto-Northwest Caucasian form "sea" is **łʷə*.

Kassian also compares Hattic *han* with Proto-Yeniseian **xän* "wave" (Kassian 2009 – 2010: 343), he reconstructs the Proto-Yeniseian form "wave" as **xän*, and also compares Hattic and Proto-Yeniseian forms with Proto-North Caucasian **x_ǎnhř* "water" (Kassian 2009 – 2010: 343).

The Hattic form is very close to the Proto-Yeniseian form and demonstrate little resemblance to the Proto-Northwest Caucasian form.

"to see"

Hattic *kun* (*gaun* / **kum*) or *kunu* "to see" (Soysal 2004: 290) correlates with Proto-Yeniseian **qo* "to see".

For Proto-Northwest Caucasian the form **p:A* for "to see" is reconstructed.

Kassian also compares Hattic *kun* with Proto-Yeniseian **qo*, and also with Proto-North Caucasian **agwV* "to see" (Kassian 2009 – 2010: 347)

It is obvious that the Hattic form is closer to Proto-Yeniseian and is much unlike the corresponding Proto-Northwest Caucasian form. Also the distance between Hattic *kun* and Proto-North Caucasian **agwV* is more significant than that between Hattic *kun* and Proto-Yeniseian **qo*.

"tongue" (and possibly "word", "speech")

The Hattic word *alep* (*alip*, *aliw*) "tongue" (and possibly "word", "speech") correlates with

Proto-Yeniseian *ʔa/Vp.

Proto-Northwest Caucasian word “tongue” and “language” is *baʒA.

Kassian also compares Hattic *alep* with Proto-Yeniseian *ʔa/Vp (Kassian: 340 – 341) and points out that the corresponding Proto-North Caucasian form is *ʒānpV “lip” (Kassian 2009 – 2010: 341)

The Hattic form is very close to the Proto-Yeniseian and is completely different from the Proto-Abkhaz-Adyghe. Also the distance between Hattic and Proto-North Caucasian forms is more significant than that between Hattic and Yeniseian forms.

“water”

Hattic *ur/uri* – “spring” / “stream”, “well” (Soysal 2004: 318) correlates with Proto-Yeniseian *xur “water”. In Proto-Northwest Caucasian the form for “water” is *bza.

For the sake of completeness of comparison, “river” in Proto-Northwest Caucasian is *χ^wV, and “small river” in Proto-Northwest Caucasian is *k^wa-

Kassian also compares Hattic *ur/uri* with Proto-Yeniseian *xur and also with Proto-North Caucasian *ħwiri “water”, “lake” (Kassian 2009 – 2010: 392).

The Hattic form is clearly very close to the Proto-Yeniseian and is completely different from the Proto-Northwest Caucasian forms.

All the lexical examples considered here, as well as the grammatical facts, clearly indicate that within the Sino-Caucasian family, the Hattic language reveals significant similarities not with the Abkhaz-Adyghe languages, but with the Yeniseian languages.

3. Ethnonyms Hatti and Ket are cognates

One day Emil Forrer suggested that perhaps the Kets are related to the Hittites, i.e., the Kets are a group of the Hittites who migrated to Siberia, because the ethnonyms Hittites and Kets sound very similar.

It should be noted here that in the first half of the 20th century, studies of the Yeniseian languages, which include Ket, were just beginning, and it was completely unclear to what family the Yeniseian languages were related. Initially, some linguists assumed that the Yeniseian languages might be related to the Indo-European family. The understanding that the Yeniseian languages are not related to Indo-European, but belong to the Sino-Caucasian family, emerged much later, only in the second half of 20th century.

However, sometimes even the erroneous judgments of great minds open up promising paths.

It is now well known that the ethnonym Hittites was borrowed by the Hittites from the indigenous people of Asia Minor - the Hattians, that is, the Hittites themselves called themselves the same as the Hattians: Hatt/Hatti, and only later, when the Hattian language was discovered, in order not to confuse the two ethnic groups, scholars agreed for convenience to call one people Hittites and the other Hattians.

The ethnonym Hatt/Hatti was apparently a self-designation of the corresponding ethnic group. It was shown above that within the Sino-Caucasian family, the Hattic language does not exhibit any particular affinity with the Abkhaz-Adyghe languages, but it does demonstrate significant

similarities with the Yeniseian languages, both at the structural and lexical levels. The same is true for the ethnonyms: Hatt and Ket.

The ethnonym Hatt (Hatti) and the ethnonym Ket (Proto-Yeniseian **keʔt*, Ket-Yugh: *kεʔt*, Assano-Kott: *hit*, **het*, Arino-Pumpokol *kit*).

The ethnonym Ket literally means "man", and the ethnonym Hatt also most probably has the same meaning.

The word-form *keʔt* and the word-form *hatt* are cognates.

To ensure that my conclusions are not speculative, I will calculate the degree of similarity between the word forms *hatt* and *keʔt*. The method of calculation of degree of similarity is described in Akulov 2025a.

[keʔt] ~ [hatt]

[k] ~ [h] = voiceless glottal fricative consonant ~ voiceless velar plosive consonant = $(2/4 + 2/4)/2 = 0.5$;

[a] ~ [e]: low front unrounded vowel ~ high-mid front unrounded vowel = $(3/4 + 3/5)/2 = 0.675$;

[ʔ] has no correspondences in the form [hatt], so in this case the degree of similarity is zero;

[t] ~ [t] = 1;

the second [t] of [hatt] correspondences in the form [keʔt], so in this case the degree of similarity is zero;

Thus, the degree of similarity of [hatt] and [keʔt] is $(0.5 + 0.675 + 0 + 1 + 0)/5 = 0.435$.

For the sake of comparison and illustration now I calculate the degree of similarity of French word *homme* [ɔm] and *hombre* [ombre], both originated from Latin homo "man".

[ɔm] ~ [ombre]

[ɔm] ~ [ombre]

[ɔ] ~ [o] = (low-mid back rounded vowel) ~ (high mid back rounded vowel) = $(4/5 + 4/5)/2 = 0.8$;

[m] ~ [m] = 1;

[b] of [ombre] has no counterparts in [ɔm], so in this case the degree of similarity is zero;

[r] of [ombre] has no counterparts in [ɔm], so in this case the degree of similarity is zero;

[e] of [ombre] has no counterparts in [ɔm], so in this case the degree of similarity is zero.

Thus, the degree of similarity of [ɔm] and [ombre] is the following: $(0.8 + 0.1 + 0 + 0 + 0)/5 = 0.36$.

The value of the degree of similarity of [hatt] and [keʔt] is higher than that of [ɔm] и [ombre].

It means that forms *hatt* and *keʔt* are completely normal variants of the same word existing in related languages.

If we compare the form *hatt* with the Assan-Kott *het*, the degree of similarity will be even greater.

[hatt] ~ [het]:

[h] ~ [h] = 1;

[a] ~ [e] = 0.675;

[t] ~ [t] = 1;

the second [t] of [hatt] has no correspondences in the form [het], so in this case the degree of similarity is zero.

The degree of similarity of [hatt] and [het] is $(1 + 0.675 + 1 + 0)/4 \approx 0.67$.

This similarity index value is significantly higher than the similarity index value of the French [ɔm] and [ombre] that is 0.36. And also is higher than the degree of similarity of Italian *uomo* [wɔmo] and French *homme* [ɔm] that is 0.5 (see Akulov 2025a: 25).

It is quite noteworthy that for the Proto-Abkhaz-Adyghe language the form *q:aça with the meaning "person", "man" is reconstructed, and it can potentially be compared with the form *hatt*.

However, the problem here is that the form *q:aça doesn't simply mean "person" / "human being" but means "male", "brave lad" / "stalwart". This form and its derivatives have never been, and are not used to refer to people in general (people as a species), nor have they been used to designate a representative of a specific ethnic group or a specific local group.

The fact that the ethnonym Hatt has a clearly visible correspondence in the Proto-Yeniseian language, while there is no such analogue in Proto-Abkhaz-Adyghe, once again confirms that the Hattians were actually a branch of the ancient Yeniseians.

4. Names of the main Hattic deities have clear Yeniseian etymologies

Names of all the main Hattic deities have clear Yeniseian etymologies.

4.1. Taru

The god Taru is one of the central deities in the Hattian pantheon. Traditionally, he is described as a classical thunder god, responsible for various weather phenomena such as thunder, lightning, thunderstorms, rain, clouds, and storms. He also rules the sky and the mountains.

It was previously suggested that the theonym Taru could be related to the Proto-Abkhaz-Adyghe *bʷabʷa "to rumble", "to thunder" (Akulov 2024: 31).

In fact, the Proto-Abkhaz-Adyghe form bʷabʷa is most likely not connected in any way with the Hattic Taru; it is possible that bʷabʷa is simply an onomatopoeia for the sounds of thunder.

Considering that within the Sino-Caucasian macrofamily the Hattic language shows significant closeness not to the Abkhaz-Adyghe languages, but to the Yeniseian languages, it seems promising to look for correspondence to the theonym Taru in the Proto-Yeniseian forms.

For Proto-Yeniseian, the form for "thunder" is reconstructed as *ʔaj[a]k. It is clear that this form has little in common with the theonym Taru.

However, for Proto-Yeniseian also has reconstructed such a word as *tVr, meaning "shake" and it's noteworthy that in Kott, this root takes the form tar.

At first glance, the verb "to shake" seems to have little to do with thunder, thunderstorms, or storms. However, it can be assumed that the Hattian Taru was not only the god of thunder and

storms, but also the god of earthquakes, and perhaps even more an earthquake god than simply a weather god.

It's no secret that Asia Minor is one of the most seismically active zones in the world. It would be extremely naïve to assume that ancient people had no understanding of natural phenomena such as volcanic eruptions and earthquakes.

For example, a fresco discovered in Çatalhöyük, depicts an eruption of the Hasan mount, along with a schematic depiction of the settlement of Çatalhöyük itself. The Hasan mount is located approximately 100 km east-northeast of Çatalhöyük (Fig. 6), and residents of Çatalhöyük regularly visited the volcano area to mine obsidian.

There is reason to suppose that the people who lived in Çatalhöyük were the direct ancestors of the Hattians.

We should also keep in mind that in various mythologies, gods responsible for weather phenomena could also be gods of earthquakes.

For example, Poseidon was the god of the sea, storms, and earthquakes. In Pylos and Thebes, where Poseidon was worshiped as the central deity, he had a special epithet – earthshaker.

In Maori mythology, there is a god named Ruumoko. Ruumoko is the god of earthquakes and volcanoes, as well as the god of the changing seasons.

It is quite characteristic that Proto-Abkhaz-Adyghe does not have reconstructed forms similar to Proto-Yeniseian **tVr*, meaning "to shake." The Proto-Abkhaz-Adyghe form **raʎa* does not mean "to shake," but "to threaten," or "to shake one's fist." The semantic distance between "to shake" and "to threaten" is nevertheless significant.

Also, in the dictionary of the Hattic language created by O. Soysal, it is said that in Hattic there is a verb *tar*, the meaning of which has not yet been determined (Soysal 2004: 312) Probably the verb *tar* could have the meaning "to shake" or something close to it.

Fig. 5. A fresco from Çatalhöyük depicting an eruption of the Hasan mount volcano (image source – Vasiloudis 2024)

Fig. 6. Location of Çatalhöyük and Mount Hasan (map has been drawn after Google maps' screenshot)

Thus, I suppose the theonym Taru originally simply meant "Shaker." And Taru's primary function was originally to control earthquakes, and he became a thunder god later. That is, when the ancestors of the Hattians lived primarily by hunting and gathering, and agriculture was still in its infancy, the most terrifying natural phenomena for them were volcanic eruptions and earthquakes. Thunderstorms and storms were initially less terrifying for hunters, because until people actively engaged in agriculture, they didn't understand that a storm could instantly destroy crops and bring a group to the brink of extinction.

Moreover, it's important to understand that ancient people's thinking was concrete and figurative, meaning they used analogies with known phenomena to explain incomprehensible natural phenomena. The ancient inhabitants of Asia Minor could have repeatedly witnessed thunder-like sounds during earthquakes and volcano eruptions, and when they heard thunder during a thunderstorm, they certainly interpreted it as someone (in this case, the god Taru) now shakes the heavenly earth, producing the same sound as usually happens during earthquakes on earth.

Here the question may arise: why is there no god like Taru in the mythologies of the Yeniseians?

First, any mythology is not a rigid set of concepts and motifs that are learned once and then simply passed on. Any mythology always reflects actual social practices and the current reality in which a particular people live.

Second, those Yeniseians who lived on the Yenisei River and in Western Siberia lived in a region where no seismic activity is observed.

Third, the Yeniseian people start to cultivate the land very late, in modern times, under the influence of Russians. And the agriculture of the Yeniseians, in general, was reduced to vegetable gardening

And, characteristically, Ket mythology doesn't even have a special thunder god. Thunder is called *Es desiy* [es desij], which literally means "cry of god" or "cry of heaven". The word *es* originally means "sky" in the Yeniseian languages, but in modern times, as the Yeniseians became quite familiar with Orthodox Christianity, their original beliefs underwent some changes, and the figure of a supreme god residing in the sky emerged in their mythology. And this god is named simply "sky", i.e., *Es*.

4.2. Eštan

The Hattian sun goddess – Wurunsemu (Furunsemu) / Eštan – is the wife of Taru and the main goddess in Hattian, and later in Hittite mythology (in Hittite mythology she was known as Ištanu).

The name Eštan is the original name of the goddess.

Currently, there are no versions of the etymology of the name Eštan.

The theonym Eštan is unlike the word for "sun" both in Proto-Yeniseian and Proto-Northwest Caucasian.

The Proto-Yeniseian word "sun" is **xiGa*; the corresponding Proto-Northwest Caucasian form is **(mV)-rəʁa*.

However, the name Eštan can be explained as a compound of two Proto-Yeniseian forms: **ʔes* "sky" and **tVn-* "to lie", "to sleep".

And thus the theonym Eštan means "lying [in] the sky".

For Proto-Abkhaz-Adyghe, two forms with the meaning "sky" have been reconstructed:

- 1) **ç^wa* / **c^wa* "star", "sky"
- 2) **z^wV* "star", "sky"

These forms can be compared with the component *eš* from the theonym Eštan, but it is quite clear that the distance between these forms and the form *eš* is much greater than the distance between the form *eš* and Proto-Yeniseian **ʔes*.

As for the meaning "to lie down", the following forms have been reconstructed for it in Proto-Abkhaz-Adyghe:

**ja* "to lie down", "to sleep"

**łə*- "to lie down",
 **sə*- "to sit", "to lie down"
 **ṗǎćV* "to lie down"

Only forms **ja* and **sə*- can be somehow compared with the component *tan*, but the distance between these forms and the component *tan* evidently is more significant than between the distance between the component *tan* and the Proto-Yeniseian form **tVn*.

4.3. Inar

The goddess Inar is one of the two daughters of Taru and Eštan. Inar is a Hattic name; the Hittites called this goddess Inara. The goddess Inar was considered the patroness of nature, the countryside, and wild animals. In her functions, she is similar to Artemis of ancient Greek mythology; both goddesses can be considered mistresses of animals.

The theonym Inar also has a fairly clear Yeniseian etymology.

In the name Inar can be singled out the component *-ar* which correlates with Proto-Yeniseian **ʔ[ā]rV* "taiga," "wilderness".

And the component *in* can be correlated with Proto-Yeniseian **ʔiń-* "to shine," "to glitter".

Thus, the name Inar can be translated as "lush forest", "blooming forest".

It is noteworthy that in Proto-Northwest Caucasian the form for "forest" is **maźV*.

4.4. Mezulla

The goddess Mezulla (or Mezzulla) is another daughter of Taru and Eštan. The name Mezulla is a Hattic word as well as above-considered theonyms. She was also known as Tappinu that means "her daughter" in Hattic. The role of Mezulla in the Hattic pantheon is actually quite vague. As the daughter of the two chief Hattic deities, she could be called upon to act as an intermediary with either of them, especially with her mother.

At present there is no complete clarity regarding the meaning of the name Mezulla, but it is supposed that the name probably expresses the meaning of diminution.

In the name Mezulla can be singled out the root *mez* that can be correlated with Proto-Yeniseian **bis-* "brother"/ "sister". The corresponding Proto-Northwest Caucasian form is **hźə*. The root *mez* is closer to Proto-Yeniseian form than to Proto-Northwest Caucasian.

At present, no exact equivalents for the component *ulla* are seen among Hattic and Proto-Yeniseian words, so its meaning can only be guessed at. However, the component *-ulla* can potentially be compared with Hattic suffix *-inu* that functions as a diminutive suffix (Soysal 2004: 222).

Thus, it is possible to state that the name Mezulla means "younger sister".

5. Conclusion

Summing up all the above-considered facts, it can be concluded that the Hattians are not ancestors of the Abkhaz-Adyghe peoples and are certainly not a branch or subethnic group of the Abkhaz-Adyghe. The Hattic language demonstrates far more similarities with the Yeniseian languages (both at the structural-grammatical level and at the lexical level) than with Abkhaz-Adyghe languages. The relationship of the Hattians to the Abkhaz-Adyghe is a rather distant one, it is a relationship within a macrofamily.

The ancestral language of Hattic, all North Caucasian languages, and Sumerian is a language that separated from the ancestral language of the Yeniseian languages. When speakers of this language, which had separated from Proto-Yeniseian, arrived in the Caucasus, the ancestral language of Hattic was the first to separate. The Hattic language separated from its ancestor-language before the separation of Sumerian and before the division of the ancestor-language into the Northeast Caucasian and Northwest Caucasian branches occurred. Therefore, Hattic cannot be the ancestor of the Northwest Caucasian languages, and certainly cannot be an Abkhaz-Adyghe dialect. The ancestor of the Abkhaz-Adyghe language appeared much later after the separation of the ancestor of Hattic.

Fig. 7. A scheme showing relationship and approximate time of divergence of languages belonging to the western branch of the Sino-Caucasian (Ainu-Minoan) macrofamily

And Hattic was a kind of relic, preserving many archaic Yeniseian forms. While the languages remaining in the Caucasus underwent various innovations, changes due to different contacts, et c. Hattic existed in relative isolation and was virtually unaffected by external influences, thus managing to preserve its identity more or less intact for a time.

The Yeniseian languages are a kind of ancestral language in relation to the North Caucasian languages, the Yeniseian languages are a branch from the ancestor of the North Caucasian languages, because a number of forms that are fossilized forms in the North Caucasian languages and difficult to explain with the help of the grammars of the North Caucasian languages, in the Yeniseian languages are productive forms and can be easily explained with the help of the Yeniseian grammar.

The history of appearance of individual languages / groups / branches and their relationships can be understood by looking at the scheme (Fig. 7) and the map (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. A map representing the history of spread of the main languages of the Aino-Minoan stock across Eurasia (image source – Akulov 2025b: 38)

Hattic is related to the North Caucasian languages, and in particular to Abkhaz-Adyghe languages also, but this is a quite distant relationship, a relationship within large language macrofamily, not within a language group. Hattic and Abkhaz-Adyghe languages belong to different groups within the Sino-Caucasian macrofamily. The difference between Hattic and Abkhaz-Adyghe languages is the same as, for instance, the difference between Balto-Slavic and Indo-Iranian languages.

All claims that Hattic is the ancestor of the Abkhaz-Adyghe languages or an Abkhaz-Adyghe dialect are based on a desire to embellish the ancient history and to claim 'great' ancestors. All statements that Hattic is closely related to the Abkhaz-Adyghe languages are unscientific nonsense with a quality mark of approximately the same level of "scientificity" as claims that, for example, "the Russian language is unusually close to Sanskrit".

The Hattic language is much closer to the Yeniseian languages than to the Abkhaz-Adyghe languages and, more broadly, to the North Caucasian languages. The fact that the Hattic language exhibits significant structural and lexical similarities with the Yeniseian languages, as well as the clear similarity between the ethnonyms hatt and keʔt/het, allows us to conclude that the Hattians were a branch of the ancient Yeniseian people.

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